

ACTUALITY OF SPEAKING IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. It is necessary to use the achievements of science and technology, especially in the fields of linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, psycholinguistics and psychology, to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. One of the advantages of the innovative educational model is the focus on teaching high-level students' personal motivation, non-standard thinking, responsibility, initiative, and the formation of their own attitude to the events around them. Such activities help to develop independence, creativity, productive and critical thinking, and also expand the educational material.

Keywords: competence, pronunciation, tools, critical thinking, motivation, skills.

INTRODUCTION

At present, one of the most important issues in education is the purpose, content, methods, tools, organizational forms, imparting knowledge and realizing the educational goal based on the subject material studied in the course of education.

New trends in language teaching were created under the influence of approach and method. However, these methods and approaches in language teaching have not been able to reveal the fundamental essence of teaching. The resulting approaches and methods served only to teach one or another area of the language. No single theory, approach or method covers the general aspects of language teaching. However, nowadays language teaching has reached a meta-theoretical stage. As a result, the language began to be interpreted on the basis of the anthropocentric theory at a new stage. It began to understand man as the central figure [1].

MAIN PART

Today's modern linguistics includes linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, discursive analysis, and the creation of interaction in foreign language teaching and the question of the personality factor in perception is the center of the object of education.

The success and efficiency of foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions is characterized by the foreign language lesson of the country of study and the uniqueness of its organization, the age characteristics of the students, the task set before this stage, its content, and the

psychological and pedagogical factors related to the beginning of foreign language teaching at this stage. The nature of foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions largely depends on how teaching is organized and conducted at the initial level of higher education [2].

Based on the scientific literature and methodical instructions on differentiating the stages of foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions, based on the comments made during pedagogical practice and the results of observing students during the course of the lesson, it can be said that when choosing the educational material for the initial stage, that is, the first academic year, this language in determining the methods of working with the material, creating exercises and organizing the lesson, it is necessary to proceed from the unique characteristics of the students. That is, in other words, all the work described above should be carried out taking into account the student's age characteristics and his worldview.

It is also necessary to always rely on thinking when developing the student's speech. A student's careful observation, trying to understand, remembering and analyzing his observations, classifying, summarizing, systematizing, explaining and proving, in cases related to reasoning, ensures the development of speech based on thinking. It is quite easy for a student to tell what he has read in a foreign language without a plan, but the teacher should teach him to plan his story, divide the read text into parts and put a title on each part, and teach him to tell it in a certain sequence. Along with the development of students' speech and thinking ability, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of their written speech, to be able to write their thoughts literately according to their level. Before organizing written activities, the teacher [5]:

- 1) conduct approximate orthographic training to prevent errors;
- 2) increase the student's ability to use dictionaries;
- 3) creative work should gradually become more complicated.

It is known that it means to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning/teaching English. Emphasis was placed on the following aspects of effective use of video materials in foreign language classes:

Psychological aspect: the selected videos increase students' interest, imagination and creativity; prevent emotional tension (stress), teach students to think critically.

Socio-cultural aspect: (1) in the selection, classification and presentation of audiovisual materials, in order to prevent various misunderstandings and conflicts arising in the process of intercultural communication, pay attention to the reflection of information about the language and culture of the country where the language is being studied; (3) the possibility of comparing the country of study and national cultures; (4) as a result, students feel the universal (common) and differences between national cultures and the culture of the country where the language is studied.

Linguistic aspect: (1) presented audiovisual materials provide students with an opportunity to hear real speech and imitate its examples; (3) serves to improve skills and competencies related to the main types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading, writing); (4) enables the grammatically correct use of lexical units appropriate to the situation in the course of natural communication.

Paralinguistic aspect: (1) a speech fragment in audiovisual materials reflects changes in the mentality of a representative of the country whose language is being studied - a unique manifestation of paralinguistic tools (emotional states: facial expressions, gestures, distance between interlocutors, clothes, etc.) in their speech, expression of objective and subjective factors affecting their speech allows students to develop verbal and non-verbal communication skills and abilities.

CONCLUSION

In short, in the process of organizing foreign language teaching, in the analysis of the problem of the image of the external world in the human psychological imagination and its reflection in the language, it is one of the most urgent problems to check their language and speech reserves, the memory of the units gathered in them, and the factors of this in teaching foreign language learners to speak a foreign language. one is counted. These problems make it necessary to apply language and speech units in an associative direction in linguistics and foreign language teaching.

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